

Synthesis of 5-Glycyl Oxazolophenoxazines

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Phthalylglycyl chloride (1) reacts with 2-aryl-5*H*-oxazolo (4,5-*b*)-phenoxazines (2) in dioxane in the presence of triethylamine to give 5-phthalylglycyl oxazolophenoxazine derivatives (3). Hydrazinolysis of (3) gives 5-glycyl oxazolophenoxazine hydrochlorides (4) in good yields. These have also been prepared by an alternative route in which chloroacetylchloride is condensed with 2-aryl-5*H*-oxazolo (4,5-*b*) phenoxazines (2) in dry benzene in the presence of pyridine to give *N*-chloroacetyl oxazolophenoxazines (5). Treatment of (5) with ammonia furnishes glycyl oxazolophenoxazines.

IN a previous publication¹ the synthesis of oxazolophenoxazines and some of their derivatives have been described. Some of these compounds showed high reactivity towards bacteria and fungi.

In the present work attempts were made to prepare 5-glycyl oxazolophenoxazines to evaluate their values as bacteriostatic agents. The fusion of phthalic anhydride with glycine gave *N*-phthalyl glycine which on treatment with SOCl_2 yielded phthalyl glycinyl chloride (1). This reacted readily with 2-aryl-5*H* oxazolo (4, 5-*b*) phenoxazines (2) in dioxane using triethylamine as a catalyst, giving 5-phthalyl glycyl oxazolophenoxazines (3). Hydrazinolysis of (3) gave the corresponding 5-glycyl oxazolophenoxazine hydrochlorides (4), as shown in Scheme 1.

The assignment of the structures (3) and (4) was based on : (i) analytical data, (ii) infrared absorption spectra, which showed peaks corresponding to an amide group near 1680-1600, 1540-1520 and 1280-1200 cm^{-1} and in the range 1695-1730 cm^{-1} corresponding to the carbonyl stretching frequencies².

Compounds (4) could also be prepared by an alternative route as shown in Scheme 2. In this procedure chloroacetylchloride was condensed with 2-aryl-5*H*-oxazolophenoxazines(2) in dry benzene using pyridine as an acid binding agent giving 5*N*-chloroacetyl oxazolophenoxazine derivatives (5). Treatment of the latter

compounds with ammonia gas gave the corresponding 5-glycyl-oxazolophenoxazine derivative, hydrochlorides of which were readily prepared by reaction with HCl gas. These hydrochlorides (4) were identical with those prepared via Scheme 1 as indicated by melting points and mixed melting points (which showed no depression). c. f. Table 4.

Scheme 2

In contrast to the parent oxazolophenoxazines testing of the compounds (4) against some strains of bacteria and fungi showed no remarkable activity, thereby indicating that the introduction of the glycinyl radical have suppressed these reactivities.

Experimental

The IR absorption spectra were determined in KBr pellets on Unicam SP 200 G grating spectrophotometer. All melting points are uncorrected.

Preparation of phthalyl glycine : A mixture of phthalic anhydride (14.8 g), glycine (7.5 g) was rapidly heated to 150°-180°, and maintained at that temperature for ½ hr. The hot melts was rapidly poured into a mortar and crushed to fine powder. Crystallization from methanol gave phthalyl glycine (16.4 g) as colourless needles m.p. 192°-194° (lit³ m.p. 192-194°).

Preparation of phthalylglycinyl chloride : Phthalyl glycine (0.61 g) in dry benzene (10 ml) was refluxed with thionyl chloride (1 ml) for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was evaporated under vacuum, and the residue was

crystallized from petroleum ether to give phthalylglycyl chloride (0.4 g) m.p. 83°-84° (lit.⁴ m.p. 83°-85°).

General method for preparation of 5-phthalylglycyl oxazolophenoxazine derivatives (3): Phthalylglycyl chloride (1 mol) in dioxane (10 ml), and triethylamine (1 mol) was refluxed with 5-H-oxazolophenoxazine derivative (1 mol) for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stand at room temperature for further 1 hr. The precipitated triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered, the filtrate was evaporated under vacuum, and the residue was crystallized from ether and recrystallized from ethyl acetate to give 5-phthalylglycyl oxazolophenoxazine derivatives. The results are listed in Table 1.

Preparation of 5-glycyl oxazolophenoxazine hydrochloride derivatives (4): 5-Phthalylglycyl oxazolophenoxazine derivatives (0.5 g) in ethanol (3 ml) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (10 ml) for 1 hour. The reaction mixture was evaporated, the dry residue was warmed at 50° for 10 min with 25 ml of 2N HCl, and allowed to stand at room temperature for ½ hr. The precipitated phthalic hydrazide was filtered, the filtrate was evaporated under vacuum till dryness to give 5-glycyl oxazolophenoxazine hydrochloride derivatives.

The results are listed in Table 2.

TABLE 1

-Ar	yield %	m.p. (°C)	Formula (Mol. wt.)	%C	Found/Calcd %H	%N
-CH ₃	85	230-32	C ₂₄ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₅ (425)	67.51 67.76	3.35 3.52	10.02 9.88
-C ₆ H ₅	90	286	C ₂₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅ (487)	71.15 71.75	3.39 3.47	8.75 8.62
-C ₆ H ₄ -o-OCH ₃	88	120-12	C ₃₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₆ (517)	69.81 69.63	3.79 3.67	7.99 8.12
-C ₆ H ₄ -o-OH	90	315-17	C ₂₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₆ (503)	69.35 69.18	3.51 3.37	8.44 8.35
-C ₆ H ₄ -o-Cl	91	160-62	C ₂₉ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₅ Cl (521.5)	66.91 66.79	2.98 3.07	8.19 8.06
-C ₆ H ₄ -p-NO ₂	93	128-30	C ₂₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₇ (532)	65.65 65.41	3.15 3.00	10.68 10.52
-C ₆ H ₄ -o-NO ₂	90	122-25	C ₂₉ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₇ (532)	65.70 65.41	3.20 3.03	10.65 10.52

TABLE 2

Ar	yield %	m.p. (°C)	Formula (Mol. wt.)	%C	Found/Calcd %H	%N
-CH ₃	85	290-93	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₃ O ₃ Cl (331.5)	58.19 58.00	4.35 4.22	12.73 12.68
-C ₆ H ₅	87	280	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₃ Cl (393.5)	64.25 64.12	4.22 4.07	10.68 10.68
-C ₆ H ₄ -o-OCH ₃	83	245	C ₂₂ H ₁₈ N ₃ O ₄ Cl (423.5)	62.65 62.41	4.33 4.25	10.02 9.92
-C ₆ H ₄ -o-OH	90	330	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₄ Cl (409.5)	61.83 61.61	4.02 3.91	10.39 10.27
-C ₆ H ₄ -o-Cl	87	309-10	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₂ (428)	59.02 58.87	3.61 3.50	9.95 9.81
-C ₆ H ₄ -p-NO ₂	88	333	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₅ Cl (438.5)	57.71 57.53	3.60 3.42	12.81 12.78
-C ₆ H ₄ -o-NO ₂	90	230	C ₂₁ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₅ Cl (438.5)	57.69 57.53	3.35 3.42	12.85 12.78

TABLE 3

Ar	yield %	m.p. (°C)	Formula (Mol. wt.)	%C	Found/Calcd %H	%N
-CH ₃	91	190	C ₁₈ H ₁₁ N ₃ Cl (314.5)	61.33 61.14	3.69 3.50	9.03 8.91
-C ₆ H ₅	88	295-97	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₃ Cl (376.5)	67.43 67.29	3.55 3.47	7.59 7.44
-C ₆ H ₄ -o-OCH ₃	90	265-67	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₄ Cl (406.5)	65.13 65.02	3.82 3.69	7.02 6.89
-C ₆ H ₄ -o-OH	93	330-31	C ₂₁ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄ Cl (392.5)	64.45 64.28	3.50 3.31	7.19 7.14
-C ₆ H ₄ -o-Cl	87	241-42	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₃ Cl ₂ (411)	61.59 61.46	3.03 2.92	6.93 6.85
C ₆ H ₄ -p-NO ₂	92	340-21	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₃ Cl (421.5)	59.96 59.85	2.89 2.85	10.03 9.97
-C ₆ H ₄ -o-NO ₂	90	233	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ N ₃ O ₃ Cl (421.5)	59.99 59.85	3.00 2.85	10.05 9.97

TABLE 4

Ar	-CH ₃	-C ₆ H ₅	-C ₆ H ₄ -o-OCH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ -o-OH	-C ₆ H ₄ -o-Cl	C ₆ H ₄ -p-NO ₂	-C ₆ H ₄ -o-NO ₂
yield %	88	90	90	87	91	90	67
m.p. °C	290-3	280	245	330	309-10	333	230

General method for preparation of 5N-Chloroacetyl oxazolophenoxazine derivatives (5).

To an equimolecular amount of 5H-oxazolophenoxazine derivatives in 15.6 ml (0.2 mol) of pyridine, and 200 ml of ClOCH₂Cl in 50 ml dry benzene was added dropwise. The reaction was carried out in an ice-water bath with stirring for 1 hr. The solvents were removed under reduced pressure and the oily residue was dissolved in 50 ml of ethyl alcohol and poured into 100 ml of cold H₂O previously acidified with 5 ml of 1 N HCl to give 5N-chloroacetyloxazolophenoxazine derivatives.

The results are listed in Table 3.

General method for preparation of 5-glycyloxy oxazolophenoxazine hydrochloride derivatives (4) according Scheme 2: 5-N chloroacetyl oxazolophenoxazine

derivatives (1 mole) was dissolved in 10 ml methanol, and saturated with NH₃ gas (for about ½ hr.) The reaction mixture was allowed to stand two days at room temperature, and then evaporated under vacuum. The residue was dissolved in 10 ml methanol, then treated with HCl gas to give the 5-glycyloxazolophenoxazine hydrochloride derivatives. The results are listed in Table 4.

References

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